

TYPES AND GENRES OF FINE ART

Rimbayeva Shaxlo Alimbayevna

Khorezm region , Gurlan district 24 school

Descriptive art and the science of drawing teacher

Abstract: Uzbekistan Republic of to independence reach of our people historical values , spiritual legacy people pedagogy traditions again to restore and them modern pedagogical technologies based on to develop big road open gave _ Especially the century to tradition have has been descriptive art types student young people attraction It is very educational important ownership with attention deserves It is also young in this respect generation each bilaterally maturity in finding our society pedagogy science , in particular art of pedagogy forward new tasks uploaded. Because it's different fields with in sync way science and art fundamental changes in the fields period is passing These changes young in generation not only theoretical knowledge take over , perhaps them in practice apply get skills formation and improvement is also required is enough

Key words: descriptive art , species , our people , culture , enlightenment , art and spirituality, various artistic materials .

Descriptive art - eng ancient and wide spread out art of types is one In fact of art types very a lot They are artistic literature , music , visual art , theater , cinema , choreography , architecture , practical decoration such as another art types are also available . Usually , true existence descriptive in images , forms spatial wide or in the plane (paper on the surface) which makes art descriptive is called art. Descriptive art concept wide to the meaning have _ until the 19th century architecture , sculpture and painting descriptive of art types boMib calculated . of the century at the end while graphics descriptive of art the most important and answer now of types to one became. The last 20 years inside of art design such as its own type place found.

Students social-cultural, spiritual-educational important owner has been this the event done to increase a lot years during national wealth being came of our people cultural and household to life wide app done beautiful from their professions one descriptive art to teach and that field according to future descriptive art teachers preparation the problem is also current in the day very big social pedagogical important has.

Of our republic in the future great to the country rotation of the world developed countries to the line in addition our people culture, enlightenment, art and of spirituality role is incomparable. Our people spirituality and culture in enrichment descriptive art itself there is a place. Current period each in the field that it was such as descriptive also major in art changes is happening Future descriptive art teacher wordless, descriptive of art expression tools about deep information have to be different artistic of materials features and of them use ways perfect acquisitions need. Descriptive art of the teacher himself pencil and paints with in color expression reach skills have to be with together, this in the field knowledge convey to his students take necessary. That's why for this in the manual painting about theoretical and Methodical data wide and around will be lit.

Fine art appeared in ancient times as a result of the development of the labor process. In the process of work, human thinking has matured, the sense of beauty has increased, concepts of beauty, comfort and usefulness in reality have expanded. With the emergence of a class society, great changes took place in social development; mental work began to separate from physical work. This was important in the development of science and art. Professional art and artists emerged during this period. Fine art has become a powerful ideological tool for promoting the ideology of the ruling class, showing its class nature. But despite this, talented artists who grew up among the masses created works that expressed the dreams of the working masses, their concepts of beauty and selfishness, nobility and humanity. People's life, behavior and customs, achievements and defeats were expressed in their works. This kind of art, which

existed in every period, depicted the beauties of life, developed high qualities and virtues in people, encouraged them to strive for equality, freedom, brotherhood, and a bright future.

In fact, the cultural values created by mankind are not only ordinary wealth, but also a mirror that reflects human intelligence and thoughts about life. To teach the history of world art, to understand the laws of its development, to get acquainted with rare monuments, to study the feelings and life experiences of people of the past means to know the formation of ideological and aesthetic views. It goes without saying. It helps people to enrich their life experiences and approach life in a wider and more comprehensive way. Types of visual arts include painting, architecture, graphics, sculpture.

Painting is one of the most important types of fine art, and is used on special canvases and walls. Color plays an important role in revealing the purpose and content expressed in works of fine art.

Monumental paintings are related to architecture, they are used to decorate the walls and ceilings of houses. Since they are intended for large-scale viewing from a distance, these are processed rounded, colors are also taken conditionally.

Miraculous works of art have been developed in different countries, including Uzbekistan, since very ancient times, and were written in ancient manuscripts. For example, Alisher Navoi's paintings of "Khamsa" are an example of this.

Easel painting works are widely used on special fabrics, cardboard, wood, framed canvas and the like. Easel painting is done in watercolor, gouache, watercolor, and tempera paints, mounted on special easels.

Through pictures made in the historical genre, we get to know the events, historical figures, and people's living culture that happened in the distant past. Historical of the genre from the looks of it one are battle scenes .

Batal Genre – "batal" in French word meaning "battle", "war" . means. It is a battle scenery in itself reflection makes. In this genre battle and military walks landscape main place occupies. Batalist - artists in his works warrior his

image heroism , bravery courage and own mother To his homeland has been infinite love is expressed. Leonardo da Vinci , M. B. Grekov , GK . Savisky, AADeyneka, VVVolkov and others are such artists.

Animalistic is a unique genre is a visual art form. SHE IS Latin "anima", "animal". The world the meaning means. An animalistic artist approaches the animal world with great interest, love and skill.

The animal world was very important in the life of primitive people . That's it period they are of the caves to the walls deer , deer , mammoths pictures those who drew

Ancient Japan and in China of animals images decorative patterns in making and monumental compositions in creating main estimated to the 16th century come animal world anatomy great painter Leonardo da Vinci and A. Dürers they worked.

Old sculptor and graph artist AND Motherland his own in his works four leggy friends truthful and reliable describes .

Training leader to the students theoretical knowledge to give in the process substantive complete open to give for live speech through speaking with together artists from his works photos , films , literature , cinema and slide films and from the slides fruitful use to the goal is appropriate .

Household genre : descriptive in art this genre works of people diary life , different events in itself embodies. The majority in the picture reflection doer household The genre was first introduced in XVII in the century living creativity reached Holland artists-Peter de Hox , Ostade , Stan , Terborch , Vermeer etc in his work manifestation will be.

References

1. . S.F.Abdirasilov. Tasviriy san'at o'qitish metodikasi. - T.: «Fan va texnologiya», 2012, 8-7 bet.

2. Zarina, Muhammadiyeva, and Qayumova Sabina. "THE PRACTICAL IMPORTANCE OF TYPES AND GENRES OF FINE ARTS IN HUMAN LIFE." *Universum: технические науки* 11-5 (92) (2021): 90-91.

3. Xamroqul Boboqulovich Raxmonqulov, Muattar Fazliddin qizi Bekkeldiyeva TerDU. Tasviriy san'at va uning mohiyati, tur va janrlari. "Oriental Art and Culture" Scientific-Methodical Journal Volume 3 Issue 2 / June 2022. 540-546 b.